

D1.4 Short Policy Brief for period 2

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EUROPEAN POLICY BRIEF

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01

**TOPIC: DEVELOPING INSTITUTIONAL OPEN ACCESS
PUBLISHING MODELS TO ADVANCE SCHOLARLY
COMMUNICATION**

PROJECT: DIAMAS

DATE: 29 JULY 2025

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Introduction

In September 2022, 23 organisations from 12 European countries started a joint effort in the DIAMAS project to better understand the institutional publishing landscape in the European Research Area (ERA); and provide the institutional publishers and service providers (IPSPs) with support to better align their practice, improve quality, and develop sustainability. This action will facilitate the work of researchers by providing them with an aligned, high-quality, and sustainable scholarly communication ecosystem, capable of implementing Open Access as a standard publication practice.

The DIAMAS project, funded by the European Commission (EC) under the Grant Agreement ID 101058007, has a duration of 36 months organised into three distinct phases:

1. Understanding the landscape of IPSPs in the ERA.
2. Improving coordination, quality and sustainability of IPSP.
3. Formulating policy and strategy recommendations.

This policy brief, released at month 35 of the project, reflects on the lessons learnt during the second phase of the project, and formulates recommendations based on the project participants' experience so far.

1. National Capacity Centres

Evidence and analysis

To date, 13 National Capacity Centres (NCCs) have been or are in the process of being established in various countries across Europe: Croatia, the Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Ireland, The Netherlands, the Nordic countries, Serbia, Spain, and Portugal. National Capacity Centres for nonprofit institutional Open Access (OA) publishing are strategically important as they are closer to the national communities, are aware of the local jurisdiction, academic traditions, and the structure of higher education. In the countries where they already exist, they play a crucial role in aligning and organising nonprofit institutional OA publishing, as we have pointed out in a previous policy brief.

Key issue: Without coordination at the European level, NCCs for nonprofit institutional OA publishing could diverge under the pressure of their national context, and duplicate effort by developing redundant tools and solutions, which would lead to a waste of resources. In addition, their needs would not be correctly addressed by the development of policy frameworks at the European and global levels.

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Policy implications and recommendations

Take measures to create National Capacity Centres in the ERA countries, and network them. Support the European Diamond Open Access Hub (EDCH) in its coordinating capacity for these NCCs. We recommend that the European Commission and national authorities provide systematic political and financial support to help develop and strengthen NCCs and their network.

2. Stable financial support

Evidence and analysis

The European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) was launched on 15 January 2025 in Madrid. The EDCH is a distributed infrastructure that offers six essential services for nonprofit institutional Open Access (OA) publishers. These are presented in Figure 1:

 DIAMOND Discovery Hub	<p>The authoritative list of Diamond OA journals that satisfy the 6 operational criteria of Diamond OA</p>		
 Resources & Guidelines	<p>A living toolsuite bringing together articles and descriptions of best practices on how to manage Diamond OA publishing</p>		
 Publishing Tools	<p>Digital resources, interoperability tools, publishing software enhancements, and add-ons.</p>		

Figure 1: the six services of the European Diamond Capacity Hub

The *Diamond OA Standard* (DOAS) service ensures quality alignment and self-assessment of Diamond OA publishers and service providers. This service responds to the fact that Diamond OA publishing efforts are relatively fragmented and of varying quality across the ERA. The *Training Platform* provides training modules and curricula for editorial staff of Diamond OA journals, again aligning the training and skills of publishing specialists across the ERA. The *Registry and Forum* service provides a platform for Diamond OA publishers to come together, and the Forum is an interactive virtual platform where all topics regarding Diamond OA can be discussed with other specialists. The *Diamond Discovery Hub* provides an authoritative list of

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Diamond OA journals that have passed the test of the 6 operational criteria defined for Diamond OA. Finally, the *Resources & Guidelines* and the *Publishing Tools* provide Diamond OA publishers and editorial staff with the necessary tools and guidelines to manage their publications.

Currently, the outputs of the DIAMAS¹ and CRAFT-OA² projects are being successfully integrated into the EDCH. Nonprofit OA institutional publishers and service providers are being onboarded in the EDCH *Registry and Forum* service. The *Diamond Discovery Hub* showcasing Diamond OA journals in the ERA has been launched. The first months of operation of the EDCH show that the community of nonprofit institutional OA publishing have eagerly been expecting this resource. The Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) self-assessment platform counts 1556 registered users and 196 DOAS self-assessments have been completed, as well as 96 sustainability self-assessments. The *Registry & Forum* service, launched in April 2025, already counts 133 registered nonprofit OA institutional publishers, and 140 individual users in the Forum. The Diamond Discovery Hub service, which is soon to be launched, now counts 2438 verified Diamond OA journals that fulfil the 6 operational criteria. Since 2022, the DIAMAS events have been attended by more than 6500 participants.

Key issue: Since its launch, and in addition to the grants provided by the European Commission via the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects, the EDCH has been generously supported by the French National Research Agency (ANR) and CNRS. Additional applications for grants are pending. However, this support in terms of grants does not provide long-term financial sustainability. In the absence of stable financial support, the EDCH will not be able to fulfil its intended role as the leading Diamond Capacity Hub in the ERA.

Policy implications and recommendations

To continue to fulfil its mission as a digital infrastructure for nonprofit institutional Open Access publishing, the EDCH needs financial stability. We recommend that the EDCH be given more stable structural financial support via the mechanism of grants to identified beneficiaries. In addition, we recommend that moral and political support be given to the paying membership model for RFOs, RPOs, and National Capacity Centers that the EDCH will develop to ensure long-term financial sustainability.

¹ <https://diamasproject.eu/about/>

² <https://www.craft-oa.eu/>

3. Open Access books

Evidence and analysis

Several initiatives have explored the possibilities of developing a model for nonprofit institutional OA publishing for academic books.³ In addition, the Recommendations formulated by the EC-funded PALOMERA project⁴ formulate an explicit recommendation to further explore the nonprofit institutional OA model for academic books. Several organisations have already started work on extending the Diamond Open Access Standard for OA journal publishers to academic books, thus initiating a much needed discussion in the academic book publishing community.⁵

Key issue: Currently, there are no calls for projects entirely dedicated to the development of the nonprofit institutional OA publishing model for academic books. There is a substantial risk that the efforts undertaken by the book publishing community will stagnate, and that this will result in a lack of alignment between nonprofit institutional OA journals and books. Open Access means that all scholarly outputs should be made available to readers, and books should not be left behind.

Policy implications and recommendations

We recommend that specific funding instruments be put in place to develop and implement nonprofit institutional OA for academic books, since books are an important output for scholarly communication in many disciplines. We again refer to the PALOMERA Recommendations for additional context (see footnote 4).

4. Scholarly societies

Evidence and analysis

Many scholarly societies⁶ have their own publications, including journals and book series. Some scholarly societies do their own publishing, sometimes as an instance of nonprofit institutional OA publishing, while others outsource this activity to commercial publishers. Scholarly societies are close to the scholarly communities they represent, and in many cases own the titles of the journals they publish. In many cases, scholarly societies own the titles of the journals they

³ The most prominent of these is the Open Book Collective (OBC). <https://openbookcollective.org>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/14049032>

⁵

<https://katinamagazine.org/content/article/open-knowledge/2025/how-should-diamond-oa-work-for-books>

⁶ Scholarly societies (a.k.a. learned societies or academies) are membership organizations that provide a platform for members to discuss the study of a specific academic discipline or a group of related disciplines.

publish. They thus control the content-related elements of publishing, one of the hallmarks of Diamond OA. The values and aims of scholarly society are close to those of Diamond OA.

Key issue: There is currently no systematic overview or analysis of the publishing activities undertaken by scholarly societies in the ERA. A better understanding of these publishing activities would be in the interest of an equitable, distributed, scholar-led nonprofit institutional scholarly communication system.

Policy implications and recommendations

We recommend that calls for projects for studies on scholarly societies include a landscape study and typology of the publishing activities of scholarly societies, and develop actions to make the EDCH services available for the publications of scholarly societies.

5. Open Research Europe (ORE)

Evidence and analysis

On 15 January 2025, 10 national research funding and performing organisations in Europe signed a Statement of Intent to support and fund ORE⁷ as a collective, not-for-profit open access publishing service for an initial period of five years, starting in 2026. This decision will likely lead to broader adoption of this innovative publication model by the researcher community. The intention was expressed to gradually seek integration of ORE with the European Diamond OA ecosystem coordinated by the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH). However, ORE is not yet entirely Diamond, as it is not open to all authors irrespective of their affiliation.

Key issue: Without further efforts that promote collaboration with EDCH, there is a risk that the journey of ORE towards the Diamond OA model remains incomplete. This would prevent ORE from achieving its full potential as the flagship Diamond OA publishing platform in the ERA.

Policy implications and recommendations

We recommend that ORE accelerate its transition towards the Diamond OA model. Coordination efforts should be put into place between ORE and the EDCH to promote further integration of ORE into the international Diamond community.

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https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/?utm_source=google&utm_medium=cpc&utm_campaign=S6996825966%20_F1000C&gad_source=1&gad_campaignid=20446596454&gbraid=0AAAAAD71x9t28IG91f01-WtSdgeefXRln&gclid=Cj0KCQjws4fEBhD-ARIsACC3d2_smTx_JKdSl04aU5UxOWiGiq4Kwh9HoN_MZ-KrOvECeDPCjZYyTcAEaAID3EALw_wcB

6. European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

Evidence and analysis

Journal articles in Open Access are very accessible for the general public: practitioners, public servants, industry leaders and researchers use search engines to find information. These users discover research articles before finding datasets. The Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) explicitly stipulates that the data underlying the article should be accessible from the article as the default, and that ideally these data should be FAIR. This means that Diamond OA journal articles function as gateways to research data, which are therefore much easier to find and access than the data repositories themselves.

Key issue: The EOSC federation is developing without taking into account publications. This creates the risk that open data and open publications develop independently without taking into account the crucial link between the two.

Policy implications and recommendations

We recommend that a more articulated relation be articulated between the EDCH and EOSC via an Open Scholarly Communication node in EOSC. The EDCH should be promoted as a set of services that facilitates access to research data via the high-quality articles and guidelines that it imposes on the nonprofit institutional OA publishers and journals it coordinates.

7. Security and sovereignty

Evidence and analysis

Scholarly communication and the independence of science are at risk. In Europe, CEU had to relocate from Budapest to Vienna due to political pressure. In the US, the editors of the most prestigious medical journals have received letters from U.S. attorneys asking questions about alleged bias in publication. In addition, proposals have been made to fund new journals that are deliberately aimed at undermining the scientific consensus around e.g. vaccination.

The for profit model of publishing is particularly vulnerable to this type of pressure, as it is highly dependent on volume of publications for its expected revenue and stock market valuation. By contrast, the nonprofit institutional OA publishing model is well suited to resist such pressure as all content-related elements of publishing are under the control of the scholarly community. The academic community should therefore be enabled to build a resilient, distributed, and sovereign

nonprofit OA publishing infrastructure that is capable of relocating endangered journals to a safer political climate. The ERA is well adapted for this purpose as it has a federal structure that is itself distributed, and allows for resilient relocation of digital infrastructure and its contents.

Key issue: Scholarly communication transcends political borders, but is vulnerable to local political pressure. There is a high risk that publications may be erased or irreversibly lost, or that journals bend to political pressure, putting scientific independence in jeopardy.

Policy implications and recommendations

The sovereignty of science must be shielded from political influence and the vulnerability of for profit publishing. We recommend that specific funding instruments be put in place to create a resilient, distributed, and sovereign scholarly communication infrastructure that would function as a safe haven for publications that wish to relocate to a nonprofit institutional OA publisher in the ERA.

Sustainability and legacy

We would like to refer to the following DIAMAS output:

Arasteh-Roodsary, S. L., Gaillard, V., Garbuglia, F., Mounier, P., Pölönen, J., Proudman, V., Rooryck, J., Saenen, B., & Stone, G. (2025). Diamond Open Access Recommendations and Guidelines for Institutions, Funders, Sponsors, Donors, and Policymakers. (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15518745>

Research Parameters

In the transition towards Open Access (OA), institutional publishing was challenged by fragmentation and varying service quality, visibility, and sustainability. To address this issue, DIAMAS gathered 23 organisations from 12 European countries, well-versed in OA academic publishing and scholarly communication. The project has:

1. Mapped the current landscape of Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) in 25 countries of the ERA with special attention for IPSPs that do not charge fees for publishing or reading. This yielded a taxonomy of IPSPs and an IPSP landscape report, a basis for the rest of the project.

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2. Coordinated and improved the efficiency and quality of IPSPs by developing a European Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing (EQSIP). This quality seal professionalised, strengthened and reduced the fragmentation of institutional publishing in Europe. EQSIP served as a benchmark for a gap analysis of the data in (1).

Buy-in and capacity-building is ensured by co-creation with the relevant IPSP communities of practice, creating a Common Access Point for IPSPs, an IPSP registry with 80% of IPSPs in the ERA, publishing guidelines, training materials, self-assessment tools, financial models, and shared cost frameworks. DIAMAS embraced diversity, equity, and inclusion by addressing gender equity in OA publishing and multilingualism in 15 European languages. Special attention was paid to building and enabling the financial sustainability of IPSPs.

3. Formulated community-led, actionable recommendations and strategies for institutional leaders, funders/sponsors/donors, and policymakers in the European Research Area (ERA). Workshops and targeted networking actions reached and engaged institutional decision-makers.

In 36 months, DIAMAS has delivered an aligned, high-quality, and sustainable institutional OA scholarly publication ecosystem for the ERA, setting a new standard for OA publishing, shared and co-designed with all stakeholders.

Project Identity

PROJECT NAME

DEVELOPING INSTITUTIONAL OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHING MODELS TO ADVANCE SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION (DIAMAS)

COORDINATOR

UNIVERSITE D'AIX MARSEILLE

CONSORTIUM

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE

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EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPÉENNE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSØ - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

FUNDING SCHEME

HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01

DURATION

September 2022 – August 2025 (36 months).

BUDGET

EU contribution: 2 518 057.50 €.

WEBSITE<https://diamasproject.eu/>**FOR MORE INFORMATION**Contact Pierre Mounier (pierre.mounier@openedition.org) and Johan Rooryck (johan.rooryck@operas-eu.org)**FURTHER READING**

List up to five current or forthcoming publications the project has produced that might be of interest to policymakers:

Arasteh-Roodsary, S. L., Gaillard, V., Garbuglia, F., Mounier, P., Pölönen, J., Proudman, V., Rooryck, J., Saenen, B., & Stone, G. (2025). Diamond Open Access Recommendations and Guidelines for Institutions, Funders, Sponsors, Donors, and Policymakers. (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15518745>

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